

Change detection of pulmonary embolism using isomeric cluster and computer vision

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ABSTRACT

Visual change detection functions in X-ray analytics and computer vision attempt to divide X-ray images toward front and backside areas. There are various difficulties in change detection such as weather changes and shadows; real-time processing; intermittent object motion; lighting variation; and diverse object forms. Traditionally, this issue has been addressed via backdrop modeling methods and the creation of custom features. We present a new feature descriptor called pulmonary embolism detection using isomeric cluster (PEDIC), uses the concept of isomerism. The isomeric and cluster isomerism characteristics of the PEDIC are distinguish it from other graphs. At isomeric thetical orientations, the cluster pattern corresponds to consecutive differences in pixel intensity between the two images. Also, the clusters are oppositely orientated, and both clusters conform to a specified isomeric feature. The local area's lines and corner point information are identified and recorded using the PEDIC in several different directions. We introduced multiresolution PEDIC, which incorporates the multiresolution Gaussian filter to achieve increased resilience in the system. We expanded our research to include rotation-invariant characteristics. We also proposed inter-PEDIC and intra-PEDIC to identify motion changes in X-ray sequences, which allowed them to extract spatiotemporal characteristics.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Digital imaging technological advancements have resulted in an unprecedented increase in X-rays and high-definition pictures, and digital image archives. The vast repositories of visual data available on the Internet have resulted in an extreme case of information overload, which has become a severe issue. In order to cope with such large amounts of visual data, robust picture indexing and efficient retrieval systems have become essential. It is critical to extract useful information from large amounts of X-ray data to maximize resource usage in a similar vein. It is necessary to detect changes in the motion of the item in X-rays to analyze and comprehend the material of interest automatically. The methods in content-based image retrieval (CBIR) and change detection are a couple of the basic low-level applications in many X-ray and computer vision processing applications. Among them are behavior analysis, biometrics, e-Commerce product cataloging, medical diagnosis, object tracking, texture matching, and visual surveillance. One of the most critical stages in creating advanced pattern recognition systems is extracting features from a dataset. A feature extraction method's success depends on selecting the feature descriptor for a particular picture or

X-ray. Visual components such as texture, form, gradients, and color are often used to feature descriptions in the earlier stated computer vision applications. It is challenging to create a feature descriptor capable of negotiating shadow, scale variations, rotation, noise, light shifts, and blur while remaining stable.

Environmental circumstances and changing backdrops also offer challenges for effective motion identification (or background removal) in X-rays, as previously stated. Furthermore, it is critical to guarantee that the feature descriptors are fast and have a low dimensionality to maintain real-time demands. Different methods have been suggested in the literature to deal with these difficulties in various ways. In order to get a thorough overview of CBIR and motion detection methods, the readers are recommended to consult the survey articles in [1]. Once it comes to the composition of an image, one of the most apparent and essential elements is the image's texture. Using texture descriptors created by hand, several computer vision applications have been successfully implemented. A local descriptor is a visual representation that uses the visual characteristics of a particular area or neighborhood to create an image representation. Recent advances in motion analysis, image retrieval, texture classification, and identification have been made possible by the use of the local binary pattern (LBP) [2] and the scale-invariant feature transform [3]. Many LBP variations have been developed to improve the discriminative capacity and resilience of the algorithm's many applications. A successful adaption of LBP variations for the previously described CBIR issue is shown in [3]. When used in X-rays, LBP histograms at the pixel level may be used to build background models and detect foreground motion to identify foreground motion. Apart from textural and spatiotemporal characteristics, local features and color fusion are some of the techniques that have been used to remove background information from images.

Whenever it refers to feature selection methods, the bulk of methods rely on the connection between the reference and its surrounding pixels to determine the characteristics of their features. Because the LBP and its variations often calculate the adjacent pattern in a single direction, it may not be easy to extract the potentially isomeric and isomeric thetical information available in the immediate neighborhood using this technique. When we talk of Isomericthetic property, we are referring to Isomeric-directional information in the immediate vicinity. In X-ray streams, medical image change detection (MICD) is a critical computer vision problem with many visual surveillance applications, traffic monitoring, synopsis creation, human-machine interaction, behavior analysis, anomaly detection, object tracking, and action identification, to name a few. The MICD method splits an X-ray picture into two distinct areas, which are referred to as the background and foreground. According to what has been said before, pre-processed X-ray frames are often utilized in higher-level processes such as image analysis. Because the result of the MICD algorithm has a significant effect on the overall performance of the following stages in high-level applications, knowing how the algorithm works are essential to understanding how the algorithm works. As a result, the technique must provide the most precise foreground/background segmentation possible. One of the advantages of MICD algorithms is that they do not need the user manually configuring the target and object masks. It is a significant advantage. This function is also in charge of backdrop creation and maintenance to distinguish between foreground and background objects. As seen in the picture, the MICD algorithms may also assist visual object tracking techniques in allocating target objects for further processing, as shown in the image. The creation of a robust MICD technique, on the other hand, is complex. Because of the many real-world difficulties that have been discussed before. As a consequence of Deep learning advances, many computer vision applications for intelligent transportation systems, notably MICD in autonomous vehicles, have seen a significant improvement. Because of their ease of accessibility and cheaper cost, X-ray-based analytics are often chosen over other modalities (such as LIDAR) in developing information technology. Change detection, also known as moving object detection, is a low-level X-ray technique widely employed in traffic analysis, intelligent surveillance, autonomous driving, and anomaly detection. Different real-world scenarios, such as changing weather conditions, variable object motion caused by different cameras' variable frame rates, shadow, intermittent object motion caused by illumination variation, heterogeneous object shapes, fluctuation in background regions, and camera jitter, make change detection difficult. Furthermore, for real-time applications in various mobile devices, the MICD techniques must operate at a high rate while using the least number of resources possible. These difficulties have been addressed in part (either separately or jointly) in the literature to some extent. Our in-depth study and analysis of the current deep MICD techniques is a critical addition to the field of ITS applications and should also be highlighted.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Many LBP variations are suggested in the literature for use in the development of CBIR systems. Using LBP, Guo *et al.* [4] transformed it to a rotationally invariant version, which lowers the dimensionality of texture classification features by restricting the number of possible rotational transformations that may be performed. The researchers created a final LBP technique, which decomposes an image into a globally

thresholded and sign-magnitude binary pattern to enhance discriminative power and reduce false positives. They also developed a distance transform-based matching method for extracting local ternary patterns (LTP), which improved the appearance of texture patterns in low-light environments. According to Zhang *et al.* [5], [6], it is possible to recover high-order local patterns by storing multiple-order local derivative directional changes in a local derivative space. Murala *et al.* [7] estimated texture retrieval performance in vertical and horizontal directions using first-order derivatives in vertical and horizontal dimensions and suggested local tetra patterns that outperformed earlier work [8] in both vertical and horizontal directions. As an additional contribution to the field, they created local maximum edge binary patterns for texture retrieval and object tracking [9], which they used in their research.

Vipparthi *et al.* [10] also addressed illumination change by creating mask maximum edge designs that maximized the amount of light that could be captured. A local mesh pattern (LMeP) was also suggested by Vipparthi *et al.* [10] for encoding the connection between the pixels' neighbors in the vicinity of a pixel. Since these LMeP patterns were retrieved at various distances, they demonstrated better biological image retrieval applications. Peak valley edge patterns, local ternary co-occurrence patterns, and directional binary wavelet patterns were all suggested by the authors for use in comparable situations, and they were all implemented. The research team of Sorensen *et al.* [11] utilized a variety of LBP-based patterns to conduct a thorough qualitative study of pulmonary fibrosis, which was followed up by studies by others [12]–[18]. Additionally, the local bit-plane decoded pattern [19] is utilized in several biological picture retrieval studies, including image retrieval from a database. Ruberto [20] developed the OT COM descriptor to evaluate texture patterns for classification purposes, which extracts and employs the Radon transform and texton matrix histogram in tandem to analyze texture patterns for classification. Recently, Song *et al.* [6] presented a diagonal texture structure descriptor to describe edge information as a receptive field characteristic, which they believe is a novel way of representing edge information. Image retrieval has also benefited from deep learning-based techniques in recent years, with promising results. Deep learning frameworks were used by Lin *et al.* [21] to develop binary hash codes for rapid picture retrieval, and their results were published in the journal *Nature Communications*. In their study, Lin *et al.* [21] developed an overall descriptor by integrating in-depth data from multiple convolutional neural networks (CNNs). However, this study uses a selected approach for convolutional descriptor aggregation that minimizes the noisy background and foreground while preserving the essential deep features [10], which contrasts with previous studies. A click feature was utilized to bridge the gap between deep features and enhance the retrieval rate. It combined high-level features from CNN and low-level features from dot-diffused block truncation coding to increase retrieval rate. Also presented was a new deep multimodal distance learning method for query-based picture ranking, developed by the researchers. Several recent studies have also used deep learning frameworks to improve the retrieval of medical images from databases. This technology is being used to develop a content-based medical image retrieval system that makes use of CNNs. Stacking denoising autoencoders and CNNs are also employed in conjunction with it to help develop computer-aided diagnostic systems.

As previously mentioned, numerous significant studies on PEDIC change detection have been published in peer-reviewed literature. Numerous outstanding surveys of traditional deep neural network, background subtraction methods for background initialization and foreground subtraction, detection with a moving camera, foreground detection, maritime surveillance, moving object, traffic monitoring, wide-area, and motion detection are contained within this collection. There are just a few research focused explicitly on deep learning-based techniques for change detection, which is a small amount compared to the overall number of studies. The study goes through the classification of various kinds of networks, which is all that is covered. Furthermore, while presenting the comparative performance assessment tables, the authors assume that all of the current techniques would be evaluated in the same way. In particular, it fails to address two critical problems linked to the assessment frameworks discussed in the literature: i) the lack of a formal evaluation framework and ii) the lack of a formal evaluation framework. Existing profound change detection techniques have distinct divisions for training and testing than they do for testing and training. Because of the disparate data-division methods used by various publications, the findings reported by different papers are incomparable to those obtained by other methodologies. As a result of using the same video frames in both the training and testing sets, the models get an unfair edge when testing them. Recently, a small number of academics have attempted to solve this problem by providing scene-independent evaluation (SIE) in films that were never viewed before. The survey does not include a comparative analysis of the various assessment techniques that have been used in the various deep learning approaches that are now available. This study provides a thorough empirical review of the existing deep learning model designs (technical characteristics) and evaluation techniques instead of prior research. We believe that this is the first attempt to evaluate and contrast the different evaluation frameworks utilized by the numerous profound change detection methods now in use, to the best of our knowledge.

3. CHANGE DETECTION USING DEEP LEARNING MODELS

Figure 1 depicts the progression of the change detection methods through time in a chronological fashion. With a colorful backdrop, the main emphasis of this research is brought to the reader's attention. As shown in Figure 1, the MICD techniques may be classified into two categories: conventional methods and deep learning-based methods. We begin by providing a high-level review of the conventional techniques. The deep learning techniques are then described in detail, including supervised and semi-supervised approaches, finetuning, pre-trained weights, various network input, and auxiliary blocks layers, among other things. Model design and other technical features of the various techniques are addressed, and the pros and cons of each method.

Figure 1. Different change detection model designs

3.1. MICD methods that are traditionally used

There are three phases to the basic framework for conventional change detection methods. The first stage is maintenance. The second stage is foreground detection, followed by feature extraction, and the third stage is background model setup. After that comes foreground detection, feature extraction, and background model setup, all of which occur in the following stages. The low-level picture characteristics, such as edge magnitudes and grayscale/color intensity, are frequently utilized in change detection methods, as shown in Figure 1. In addition, super pixel-based capabilities have been included. Aside from that, Spatio-temporal characteristics and particular spatial descriptors have been developed to improve overall performance. Background model maintenance and initialization: Background modeling methods may be divided into many categories, including hybrid and other approaches, nonparametric approaches, parametric approaches, and conventional learning-based parametric approaches.

In different classifiers, the distribution is modeled and updated at each site using statistical models such as Expectation Maximization algorithms and a Gaussian mixture, which are both used in the research. Zivkovic and colleagues [22] made substantial improvements to the MOG by including variable parameter selection, Gaussian spatial mixing, and rapid initialization. The literature has also shown that these models and other statistical models such as the Dirichlet distribution, Poisson distribution, and Regression models may be extended in a variety of ways. Alternative methods to parametric statistics are those that do not depend on statistical sampling. Nonparametric approaches are mainly influenced by statistical techniques such as consensus-based and kernel density estimation, described below. A seminal paper by Yamasaki [23]

suggested three essential background model maintenance policies: a long-term history memoryless updating technique, random background sample replacement to represent short-term history, and geographic dispersion through background sample propagation. Many of the most advanced change detection methods available today use some combination of these tactics to different degrees. Decision thresholds for learning rates were updated using adaptive updating rules, which were previously unavailable. The model upgrade also included foreground segmentation and adaptive updating techniques for decision thresholds previously not included. Furthermore, an adaptive feedback system was created to continuously check the accuracy of the backdrop model and the entropy of segmentation and change the parameters as needed. Mandal and colleagues [10] presented a deterministic approach for updating background models, successfully implemented in practice.

Traditional learning methods are still in widespread use. There have also been many learning-based methods introduced into the literature, such as support vector machines (SVM), principal component analysis (PCA), and neural networks (NN). The self-organizing background subtraction algorithm, a real-world application of neural networks, was developed using the 2D self-organizing neural network design. It learns in a self-organizing way and uses what it has learned to construct the picture sequence and neural background model while preserving pixel spatial connections in the process. A winner-take-all function and a technique for updating local weights of neurons are implemented, allowing for learning to be spatially restricted to the immediate surrounding area of the most active neurons. As a result, it operates as a competitive neural network, and its performance is comparable to that of a competitive neural network. Several enhancements compared to previous models have also been identified. Background removal has been accomplished at various levels via the use of SVM models. Cheng *et al.* [24] developed an online learning system that monitors temporal changes over time by using one-class support vector machines (1-SVMs) to regulate spatial interactions, and they published their findings in science. Furthermore, Han *et al.* [1] calculated background probability vectors for a collection of characteristics and then used a support vector machine to eliminate the background probabilities from the model (SVM). Others have looked at using SVM models to detect changes similar to what we are doing here. It has been decided to use the PCA for subspace learning to deal with the variations in lighting across video episodes. Previously, discriminative models and mixed subspace learning were used in conjunction with one another. In contrast, regular subspace models are susceptible to outliers, noise, and missing data; as a result, they are inappropriate for a wide range of applications. The development of robust principal component analysis-based models, which estimate the background as a low-rank component and the foreground as a sparse matrix, has been undertaken to solve these concerns. It was shown how to create robust spatiotemporal subspaces for dynamic movies using a dynamic movie generator. Many incremental efforts are also made to enhance the PCA models' overall performance to improve the model's overall performance. Various studies have merged several modalities of algorithms in order to enhance the overall performance of such algorithms. In their study, Bianco *et al.* [25] conducted many tests using genetic programming to integrate different change detection methods. They suggested that multiple background models, such as a fusion of the YCbCr and RGB color models, be used to determine the background probability of a change detection methodology. In a similar vein, segmentation inclusion is one of the other exciting hybrids that the researchers have revealed. Supattra Puttinaovarat *et al.* [26] presents technical development of a toolbox for rivers classification and their change detection from Landsat images, by using water index analysis and four machine learning algorithms, which are KMeans, ISODATA, maximum likelihood classification (MLC), and support vector machine (SVM).

There are other options. In addition to traditional methods, several additional non-conventional ways have also proven effective in background removal. The researchers suggested another set of exciting techniques to address the difficulties in motion identification: edge-based foreground segmentation, local codebook-based models, motion modeling, physics-based change detection, graph cut, and optical flow. Fuzzy models, on the other hand, have also been investigated in the literature. It is possible to get a more in-depth classification of conventional change detection methods. Regarding foreground detection, the available research suggests that threshold-based segmentation combined with post-processing methods is the most frequently utilized approach in the field. In addition, a slew of strategies has been suggested to update the foreground segmentation criteria adaptively. In addition, the current frame and fuzzy similarity between background models have been assessed using interval similarity and membership values, as well as membership values. P. Rambabu, *et al.* [27] proposed optimal thresholding technique using fuzzy Otsu (OT-FO) method to improve the image quality.

3.2. Deep CNN method

Several computer vision tasks, including picture classification, object identification, segmentation, visual object tracking, and action detection, to name a few, have been improved by deep learning methods over the last decade. In this Figure 2, we used a conditional generative adversarial networks (cGAN) strategy for haze removal, which was presented by and is separated into two types of networks: generator networks

and discriminator networks. Instead of using the usual residual architecture with single frame as depicted in Figure 2(a), we have used the the encoding/decoding block is composed of a convolution/deconvolution layer with three frames as shown in Figures 2(b) and 2(c), followed by a rectified linear unit (ReLU). we incorporate the inception module in the residual architecture in order to improve its learning capability as depicted in Figure 2(d). We present ResINet, a generator network for frame-wise haze removal that incorporates both residual and inception ideas. ResINet is a contraction of the term's residual and inception. Predict the architecture of the proposed ResINet is depicted in Figure 2(e).

Figure 2. The change detection methods with (a) single frame, (b) three frames Conv, (c) 3×3 DeConv, (d) inception module, and (e) architectural flow

In addition, we show the ground-breaking deep learning methods and datasets to identify changes in consecutive figures. We provide the results of an empirical investigation into these deep learning techniques. Several researchers have recently utilized convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to divide video frames into the foreground and background areas, a method known as change detection. CNNs are a kind of neural network that learns from experience. Creating CNN models for MICD presents a different set of difficulties than developing CNN models for video-based or other pictures. Spatial domain characteristics, such as segmentation, object identification, and picture classification, for example, can only be learned in the spatial domain and cannot be learned anywhere else. When dealing with single image-based decision-making issues, the spatial dimension characteristics are adequate to meet the application's needs. It is not essential to take into account the characteristics of the time dimension in these activities. As a result, the models developed for these tasks do not function correctly in the MICD environment.

In action recognition, the characteristics collected from both the temporal and spatial dimensions are utilized to predict high-level categorization labels, which are then used to categorize the actions based on their classification. For the MICD, on the other hand, the creation of a spatiotemporal feature learning framework and the prediction of low-level packed pixel-wise labels are necessary prerequisites. The combination of these variables makes the task of building and developing deep learning models for MICD challenging. The following features of the most current deep MICD techniques are discussed in more detail in Table 1.

2. Pattern with several resolutions as part of the multiresolution Gaussian filter integration, PEDIC integrates PEDIC. It has been shown in the field that the multiresolution Gaussian filter may be used effectively, as local derivative designs demonstrated in LBP [3].

$$L(a, b, \sigma) = g(a, b, \sigma) * I(a, b)$$

$$g(a, b, \sigma) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma^2} e^{-(a^2+b^2)/2\sigma^2}$$

$$MPEDIC_{p,r}^{\sigma,\theta}(p, q) = PEDIC_{p,r}^{\theta}(L(p, q, \sigma))$$

3. Feature representation and matching methods are both critical in the development of any pattern recognition applications.

$$Hist_{\sigma} = \sum_{a=1}^M \sum_{b=1}^N \delta(MPEDIC_{p,r}^{\sigma,\theta}(p, q) - (nd, vd, pd, hd))$$

for $0 \leq pd \leq W - 1$, $0 \leq hd \leq W - 1$,
 for $0 \leq vd \leq W - 1$, for $0 \leq nd \leq W - 1$,

4. The PEDIC feature response map histogram to provide a robust picture is utilized as a feature vector. In order to calculate the intra-PEDIC for a given picture, we use the following equations:

$$\text{intra PEDIC}(a, b) = \bigoplus_{i=1}^p D_t(x_{t,u}, x_{t,i}, x_{t, \text{mod}(i,p)+1})$$

$$D(z_1, z_2, z_3) = \begin{cases} 00, & \text{if } |z_2 - z_1| > \tau \cdot z_1 \setminus |z_3 - z_2| > \tau \cdot z_1 \\ 01, & \text{if } |z_2 - z_1| > \tau \cdot z_1 \setminus |z_3 - z_2| \leq \tau \cdot z_1 \\ 10, & \text{if } |z_2 - z_1| \leq \tau \cdot z_1 \setminus |z_3 - z_2| > \tau \cdot z_1 \\ 11, & \text{if } |z_2 - z_1| \leq \tau \cdot z_1 \setminus |z_3 - z_2| \leq \tau \cdot z_1 \end{cases}$$

5. The inter-PEDIC for a given picture is calculated using the following mathematical equations:

$$\text{interPEDIC}(a, b) = \bigoplus_{i=1}^p D(x_{t-1,u}, x_{t-1,i}, x_{t, \text{mod}(i,p)+1})$$

$$D(z_1, z_2, z_3) = \begin{cases} 00, & \text{if } |z_2 - z_1| > \tau \cdot z_1 \& |z_3 - z_2| > \tau \cdot z_1 \\ 01, & \text{if } |z_2 - z_1| > \tau \cdot z_1 \& |z_3 - z_2| \leq \tau \cdot z_1 \\ 10, & \text{if } |z_2 - z_1| \leq \tau \cdot z_1 \& |z_3 - z_2| > \tau \cdot z_1 \\ 11, & \text{if } |z_2 - z_1| \leq \tau \cdot z_1 \& |z_3 - z_2| \leq \tau \cdot z_1 \end{cases}$$

6. Bit-stream and Color and the Intra-PEDIC for each color channel define the pixel-level background model described in detail.

$$BM(a, b) = \{s_i(a, b)\}_{i=1}^Q$$

7. Stop.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As per current research, LBP-based descriptors extract features concerning the relation among a reference pixel and its neighbors within a specified radius of the reference pixel. Additionally, the ternary version of the LBP is created by extracting this connection from the LTP, which is a three-valued function that is then used to construct the LBP from the LTP. The discriminative robustness and noise resistance of a feature descriptor are two essential characteristics to take into consideration. Many LBP versions published in the literature, including those depicted in Figure 3, have been unsuccessful in extracting lines and corner point information in the following neighborhood (LBDP, LBP, and LMeP). In response to this problem, we developed PEDIC, conducted significant research, and determined the benefits of PEDIC over currently available methods. Infiltration is a term that is occasionally used to describe the invasion of cancer cells into the underlying matrix or the blood vessels as part of a disease progression. Another use for this phrase is to describe the buildup of amyloid protein in the bloodstream. During leukocyte extravasation, white blood cells

migrate from inside the bloodstream into sick or infected tissues in response to cytokines, and they typically move in the same direction as a chemical gradient in a chemotaxis process. Infiltration is the expression used to represent the presence of lymphocytes in more significant numbers than usual in a tissue as depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Pulmonary embolism disease process

Local anesthetics may be administered at more than one site to permeate a region before a surgical operation as part of medical intervention [29]. Extravasation or “tissuing” are terms that may refer to unintentional iatrogenic leaking of fluids following phlebotomy or intravenous drug administration techniques, a process that is also known as extravasation or “tissuing.” [30]–[32]. Lung opacification is defined as reducing the gas to soft tissue (including blood, lung parenchyma, and stromal cells) inside the lung. As presented in Figure 4, when examining a chest radiograph or CT scan for increased attenuation (opacification), it is critical to identify the location of the increased attenuation (opacification). The patterns may be classified into three categories: opacification of the airspace, lines, and dots.

Figure 4. Pulmonary embolism identifying lung opacity

As a result of looking at the referred sample in Figure 5, we can conclude that the suggested PEDIC technique can distinguish between shadow areas and object regions. Because the intensity levels in the shadow and foreground are almost identical, the intensity-based thresholding method would be ineffective in this situation. It means that both the Intra and inter-PEDIC algorithms presented here can identify changes under difficult visual circumstances. A detailed comparison of both the proposed descriptor and current descriptors is presented in this part of the paper.

Figure 5. Identifying pleural effusionpulmonary embolism using PEDIC

6. CONCLUSION

This study presents the results of this paper, which examines current medical image change detection techniques in terms of model design and assessment frameworks. Change detection is investigated using a range of current deep learning architectures, and the efficacy of different deep learning architectures for change detection is investigated. It is necessary to split the MICD techniques into main categories and their related subclasses to give a thorough evaluation. It is shown in this paper that a complete feature descriptor for CBIR and change detection applications has been developed. Designed in the spirit of isomerism, the PEDIC makes use of both the PEDIC and clustering characteristics to achieve its goals. In part, this is due to the proposed texture descriptor's ability to extract line and corner point information from the immediate neighborhood, which is considered to be a robust texture descriptor. Additionally, just four isomeric cluster patterns are required to extract all directional information.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Han and L. S. Davis, "Density-based multifeature background subtraction with support vector machine," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 34, no. 5, pp. 1017–1023, May 2012, doi: 10.1109/TPAMI.2011.243.
- [2] M. Srinivasa Rao, V. Vijaya Kumar, and M. Krishna Prasad, "Texture classification based on local features using dual neighborhood approach," *International Journal of Image, Graphics and Signal Processing*, vol. 9, no. 9, pp. 59–67, Sep. 2017, doi: 10.5815/ijgisp.2017.09.07.
- [3] S. T. Cochran, K. Bomyea, and J. W. Sayre, "Trends in adverse events after IV administration of contrast media," *American Journal of Roentgenology*, vol. 176, no. 6, pp. 1385–1388, Jun. 2001, doi: 10.2214/ajr.176.6.1761385.
- [4] E. Guo *et al.*, "Learning to measure change: fully convolutional siamese metric networks for scene change detection," Oct. 2018, arXiv:1810.09111.
- [5] J. Zhang *et al.*, "X-Net: a binocular summation network for foreground segmentation," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 71412–71422, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2919802.
- [6] W. Song *et al.*, "Taking advantage of multi-regions-based diagonal texture structure descriptor for image retrieval," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 96, pp. 347–357, Apr. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.eswa.2017.12.006.
- [7] S. Murala, R. P. Maheshwari, and R. Balasubramanian, "Directional binary wavelet patterns for biomedical image indexing and retrieval," *Journal of Medical Systems*, vol. 36, no. 5, pp. 2865–2879, Oct. 2012, doi: 10.1007/s10916-011-9764-4.
- [8] S. Murala and Q. M. J. Wu, "Local mesh patterns versus local binary patterns: biomedical image indexing and retrieval," *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 929–938, May 2014, doi: 10.1109/JBHI.2013.2288522.
- [9] P. W. Patil, S. Murala, A. Dhall, and S. Chaudhary, "MsEDNet: multi-scale deep saliency learning for moving object detection," in *2018 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics (SMC)*, Oct. 2018, pp. 1670–1675, doi: 10.1109/SMC.2018.00289.
- [10] M. Mandal, L. K. Kumar, and S. K. Vipparthi, "MOR-UAV: a benchmark dataset and baselines for moving object recognition in UAV videos," in *Proceedings of the 28th ACM International Conference on Multimedia*, New York, NY, USA: ACM, 2020, pp. 2626–2635.
- [11] L. Srensen, S. B. Shaker, and M. de Bruijne, "Quantitative analysis of pulmonary emphysema using local binary patterns," *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 559–569, Feb. 2010, doi: 10.1109/TMI.2009.2038575.
- [12] P. D. Stein *et al.*, "Multidetector computed tomography for acute pulmonary embolism," *New England Journal of Medicine*, vol. 354, no. 22, pp. 2317–2327, Jun. 2006, doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa052367.
- [13] M. Srinivasa Rao, V. Vijaya Kumar, and M. H. M. Krishna Prasad, "Texture classification based on statistical properties of local units," *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, vol. 93, no. 2, pp. 246–256, 2016.
- [14] R. Tanaka *et al.*, "Development of pulmonary blood flow evaluation method with a dynamic flat-panel detector: quantitative correlation analysis with findings on perfusion scan," *Radiological Physics and Technology*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 40–45, Jan. 2010, doi: 10.1007/s12194-009-0074-1.
- [15] R. Tanaka *et al.*, "Pulmonary blood flow evaluation using a dynamic flat-panel detector: feasibility study with pulmonary diseases," *International Journal of Computer Assisted Radiology and Surgery*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 449–455, Sep. 2009, doi: 10.1007/s11548-009-0364-4.
- [16] R. Tanaka *et al.*, "Evaluation of pulmonary function using breathing chest radiography with a dynamic flat panel detector," *Investigative Radiology*, vol. 41, no. 10, pp. 735–745, Oct. 2006, doi: 10.1097/01.rli.0000236904.79265.68.
- [17] R. Tanaka *et al.*, "Detection of pulmonary embolism based on reduced changes in radiographic lung density during cardiac beating using dynamic flat-panel detector: an animal-based study," *Academic Radiology*, vol. 26, no. 10, pp. 1301–1308, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.acra.2018.12.012.
- [18] H. Watanabe *et al.*, "Impact of earthquakes on risk for pulmonary embolism," *International Journal of Cardiology*, vol. 129, no. 1, pp. 152–154, Sep. 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.ijcard.2007.06.039.
- [19] S. R. Dubey, S. K. Singh, and R. K. Singh, "Local bit-plane decoded pattern: a novel feature descriptor for biomedical image retrieval," *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*, vol. 20, no. 4, pp. 1139–1147, Jul. 2016, doi: 10.1109/JBHI.2015.2437396.
- [20] C. Di Ruberto, "Histogram of radon transform and texton matrix for texture analysis and classification," *IET Image Processing*, vol. 11, no. 9, pp. 760–766, Sep. 2017, doi: 10.1049/iet-ipc.2016.1077.
- [21] K. Lin, H.-F. Yang, J.-H. Hsiao, and C.-S. Chen, "Deep learning of binary hash codes for fast image retrieval," in *2015 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops (CVPRW)*, Jun. 2015, pp. 27–35, doi: 10.1109/CVPRW.2015.7301269.
- [22] Z. Zivkovic, "Improved adaptive gaussian mixture model for background subtraction," in *Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Pattern Recognition*, 2004, vol. 2, pp. 28–31, doi: 10.1109/ICPR.2004.1333992.
- [23] Y. Yamasaki, K. Abe, K. Hosokawa, and T. Kamitani, "A novel pulmonary circulation imaging using dynamic digital radiography for chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension," *European Heart Journal*, vol. 41, no. 26, pp. 2506–2506, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1093/eurheartj/ehaa143.
- [24] Li Cheng and Minglun Gong, "Realtime background subtraction from dynamic scenes," in *2009 IEEE 12th International Conference on Computer Vision*, Sep. 2009, pp. 2066–2073, doi: 10.1109/ICCV.2009.5459454.
- [25] S. Bianco, G. Ciocca, and R. Schettini, "Combination of video change detection algorithms by genetic programming," *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 21, no. 6, pp. 914–928, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1109/TEVC.2017.2694160.
- [26] S. Puttinaovaratt *et al.*, "River classification and change detection from landsat images by using a river classification toolbox," *IAES International Journal of Artificial Intelligence (IJ-AI)*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 948–959, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijai.v10.i4.pp948-959.
- [27] P. Rambabu and C. N. Raju, "The optimal thresholding technique for image segmentation using fuzzy otsu method," *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research*, vol. 10, no. 13(2015), pp. 33842–22846.
- [28] S. V. Konstantinides *et al.*, "2019 ESC guidelines for the diagnosis and management of acute pulmonary embolism developed in collaboration with the european respiratory society (ERS)," *European Respiratory Journal*, vol. 54, no. 3, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.1183/13993003.01647-2019.
- [29] H. Miyatake, T. Tabata, Y. Tsujita, K. Fujino, R. Tanaka, and Y. Eguchi, "Detection of pulmonary embolism using a novel dynamic flat-panel detector system in monkeys," *Circulation Journal*, vol. 85, no. 4, pp. 361–368, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1253/circj.CJ-20-0835.
- [30] K. M. Moser, "Frequent asymptomatic pulmonary embolism in patients with deep venous thrombosis," *JAMA: The Journal of the American Medical Association*, vol. 271, no. 3, Jan. 1994, doi: 10.1001/jama.1994.03510270069042.
- [31] M. Sakuma *et al.*, "Acute pulmonary embolism after an Earthquake in Japan," *Seminars in Thrombosis and Hemostasis*, vol. 32, no. 8, pp. 856–860, Nov. 2006, doi: 10.1055/s-2006-955468.
- [32] S. Elyassami and A. Ait Kaddour, "Implementation of an incremental deep learning model for survival prediction of

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